

Modelling for integrated national energy planning in Kenya: exploring clean cooking pathways across scales

Authors: Leonhard Hofbauer¹, Mary Kisaka², Alois Mbutura², Ariane Millot³, Pietro Lubello¹, Michelle Akute⁴, Geoffrey Murugami², Martin Kitetu², Steve Pye¹

¹: UCL Energy Institute, University College London, Central House, 14 Upper Woburn Place, London, WC1H 0NN, United Kingdom

²: EED Advisory, 50 Hamisi Road, Kileleshwa, Nairobi, Kenya

³: Department of Chemical Engineering, Imperial College London, London SW7 1NA, UK

⁴: Energy and Petroleum Regulatory Authority (EPRA), Nairobi 42681-00100, Kenya

Summary

Meeting both development and climate ambitions of low- and middle-income countries requires energy system transformations that hinge on concerted action across different levels of government. In Kenya, the government is implementing an innovative energy planning framework integrating planning both across sectors, as well as national and county levels into an Integrated National Energy Plan (INEP). With energy system modelling already supporting national and county-level planning, it is key such efforts also take into account this multi-level framework, and support coordination and a mutual understanding across government levels. In this paper, we introduce a novel county-resolved whole energy system model for Kenya aimed at supporting this process, and apply it for a scenario analysis of the clean cooking transition. The analysis highlights the diverging roles clean cooking solutions are likely to play across counties, with implications for county planning and national policy. Considering selected county plans, it also reveals how current county and national planning are not aligned. This highlights the role such modelling efforts can play in providing coherent insights and supporting dialogue across county and national stakeholders that will be crucial for the successful implementation of the INEP.

Introduction

For many low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), achieving sustainable development goals is closely intertwined with an expansion and transformation of the energy system. Many of the United Nations' (UN) Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are closely linked with the provision of clean and sustainable energy¹. Yet, the complexity of the energy system across technical, economic, and social dimensions makes this a unique governance challenge that not only requires strong action from national governments but also involvement of subnational authorities and other stakeholders,

including public utilities and private sector companies². Fostering energy system transformations that meet development and climate ambitions will require coordinated plans and concerted action across national and subnational governments^{3,4}.

In Kenya, the government is looking to drive the country's energy policy objectives through an innovative integrated energy planning process – integrating planning across different energy subsectors and, crucially, both county and national governments. While Kenya is a unitary state with sovereignty only exercised at the national level, its constitution of 2010 established 47 county governments and devolved substantial powers from the national government, including planning related to electricity and gas, as well as energy regulation⁵. Based on the principles of devolution set out in the constitution, the Energy Act 2019 established the Integrated National Energy Plan (INEP) as a framework for multi-level governance of the energy system⁶. The INEP requires counties, alongside national service providers, to prepare energy plans, which are subsequently integrated to form the INEP. County energy plans (CEPs) are strategic plans for the energy sector setting out the county's priorities and strategic direction, including to support investment in local infrastructure⁷. Plans are meant to focus on five key sectors, energy resources, energy access, energy efficiency, bioenergy, and electricity – with the former four to be explicitly captured as chapters of each CEP – while also capturing cross-cutting issues like gender equality, disability and social inclusions⁸.

Energy system modelling plays an important role in supporting decision-making and energy planning at the national and increasingly at subnational levels⁹. In Kenya, energy system models have, for example, been used to support the development of the Least Cost Power Development Plan (LCPDP) and electric cooking strategy by the national government^{10,11}. At the county level, various different tools have been used to underpin the development of county energy plans¹². While models evidently already play a role in energy planning processes, it has been argued that modelling approaches – often stemming from high-income contexts – require methodological advancements to increase relevance of modelling insights in LMIC contexts¹³. This includes, for example, efforts to increase context-specificity, better capture uncertainty, and the integration of interlinked systems.

Modelling innovation is specifically also required in the light of the multi-level governance arrangements that underpin the Kenyan and other energy systems. Previous modelling studies have generally overlooked such governance structures and thus risk providing incoherent policy insights and entrenching isolated decision-making and planning⁴. In contrast, energy modelling that is reflective of underlying multi-level governance systems can support integration of planning across scales by facilitating coordination and a mutual understanding of strategic policy directions¹⁴.

This can be based on two broad functions that models can play in the planning process¹⁵. First, models can play an analytic role in providing evidence and insights to support

decision-making. If models provide such insights that are coherent across and take into account different planning scales, they can help build a common understanding across different government levels. Second, models can function as a tool for engagement, supporting discussions among stakeholders. Modelling that is salient for more than one scale can function as a boundary object and support discussions and coordination between different levels of government^{16,17}. Both of those functions are relevant in the context of integrated county-national energy planning in Kenya. Yet, energy modelling efforts in Kenya are generally focused on the national, or to a lesser extent county level, but do not integrate both^{4,18}. Similar limitations in the modelling practice can be observed in other contexts⁴.

One of the key energy policy objectives for the INEP is universal access to clean cooking⁸. In 2022, around 69% of Kenyan households still relied on traditional fuels, in particular firewood and charcoal, for cooking energy, with negative social, environmental and economic implications¹⁹. Over the past years, the Kenyan government has developed a number of strategies to chart out and foster a transition to clean cooking for all. This includes in particular the Kenya National Cooking Transition Strategy (KNCTS)¹⁹, which sets out a target of achieving universal access to clean cooking by 2028, the Kenya National electric Cooking Strategy (KNeCS)¹¹, but also other interlinked sectoral strategies, for example, its bioenergy strategy²⁰. On the other hand, clean cooking is also meant to be a key component in county energy plans and counties' role in shaping a local clean cooking transition is highlight both in the KNCTS and KNeCS⁸. This is also reflected in CEPs developed over the past years. For example, the county energy plans of Kitui, Kiambu, and Nyandarua all discuss policy efforts and explore pathways to clean cooking in the county²¹⁻²³.

Yet, these planning efforts have largely been isolated efforts with limited integration, in particular across county and national levels²⁴⁻²⁶. This applies both to the involvement in the development, as well as the strategic direction provided by these efforts. For example, while the KNeCS makes clear recommendations on the integration of electric cooking into county energy planning, the transition scenario underpinning the strategy is presented as aggregate national pathway for urban and rural areas that does not capture the diversity of counties and how this would shape a transition to clean cooking. This stems at least partly from the energy modelling underpinning the pathway – which is based on a national model that does not represent counties explicitly^{27,28}. The development of the strategy involved a wide range of stakeholders, but it appears not to acknowledge input from county stakeholders¹¹. Moving towards an integrated county-national energy plan will require a focus on dialogue and coordination to ensure such strategies and plans, with regard to clean cooking and other policy areas, at national and county level are aligned and mutually reinforcing.

In this study, we introduce a novel multi-scale whole energy system model as tool to support county-national integration as part of the INEP process, and apply it for a scenario analysis focused on clean cooking. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this is the first quantitative modelling analysis bridging multiple governance scales in Kenya, adding to a limited amount of any such studies in LMIC context. It is embedded in a key policy effort aimed at supporting the INEP, and stems from discussions with relevant stakeholders in Kenya, including national power system planners, the Council of Governors, and county governments. The COunty-REsolved Whole Energy System Model (CORE-WESM) is a national energy system model with county representation that can support dialogue and coordination across scales. Development of such a model within a LMIC context is challenging not least due to limited availability of spatially disaggregated datasets and the nascent stage of planning processes, as highlighted by the limited number of published county energy plans and data. Hence, CORE-WESM follows a hierarchical approach to data inputs. In the first instance, this entails the creation of a downscaled version of an established national energy system model. This first-order but complete model can start functioning as a tool for analysis and engagement. It provides the basis for improvements in further steps in the hierarchical approach, including county-resolved national datasets, and data from county plans as they become available during the INEP process. CORE-WESM is described in more detail in the Method section.

Using a case study application of CORE-WESM focused on clean cooking, we highlight the way the model can support the move to more integrated planning across scales. In particular, we use the model to analyse scenarios underpinning the government's electric cooking strategy. While modelling of these scenarios for the strategy itself provided a crucial quantitative framework to consider national targets, this work considers how these scenarios could translate into county-specific pathways. While national and county-specific strategies and targets should be based on dialogue and co-creation between governments, the analysis shows how the model – in contrast to previous tools – could support such a dialogue by considering pathways and insights towards clean cooking across scales.

Results

The analysis considers three scenarios that have previously been developed and assessed during the development of the KNeCS to inform technology-specific targets in the strategy and assess their implications. The Business-As-Usual (BAU) scenario assumes continuing trends and policies without additional policy interventions towards clean cooking. The Stated Policies (SP) scenario assumes implementation of previously committed policies, including the target of universal access to clean cooking by 2028, as well as technology-specific targets, e.g., for biofuel and LPG. The analysis, in line with the KNeCS, considers improved biomass and charcoal stoves, in addition to modern

cookstoves, e.g., electric, LPG, biofuel, and biogas stoves, as clean cooking solutions available to meet this target. The e-cooking transition (KNeCS) scenario was developed as a balanced pathway to achieve the government's clean cooking targets based on stakeholder engagement during the development of the strategy. It is the pathway adopted by the government and underpins the KNeCS¹¹. Modelling efforts for the KNeCS also included a constrained and unconstrained net zero scenario, yet these are less policy relevant and thus not included here²⁸.

The scenarios are implemented by using the results of the energy modelling conducted for the KNeCS, which defines the national aggregate use of cooking stoves in rural and urban areas across the three scenarios. For integration into CORE-WESM, the national adoption pathways are disaggregated to the county level taking into account county characteristics, in particular urban-rural split, baseline stove use, household electricity access rates, and market segmentation. The scenario implementation is further explained in the Method section.

Figure 1 provides a national view from CORE-WESM on the stove transitions underpinning the scenarios – as analysed previously to support national decision-making for the KNeCS. The baseline use of cookstoves is dominated by traditional woodstoves (76%) in rural areas, while LPG stoves (64%) provide the majority of cooking energy in urban areas, with considerable contributions from traditional charcoal (15%) and woodstoves (9%). The demand for cooking energy increases steadily from 152 PJ in 2020 to 272 PJ in 2050 across all scenarios, with most of the increase in urban areas, following urbanisation trends.

Figure 1: Household cooking energy provision by cookstoves for the three scenarios, for national (total), urban and rural areas. Please note the varying y-axis scales for the three rows.

In line with the nature of the scenario, the BAU scenario only sees limited shifts in the use of stoves. In rural areas, the use of traditional firewood stoves is slowly replaced by improved woodstoves as well as LPG stoves, yet traditional stoves are still used in 2050. In urban areas, LPG stoves continue to dominate with limited increases in the use of bioethanol and electric stoves, and a shift from traditional to improved woodstoves.

In contrast, both the SP and KNeCS scenario see swift stove transitions in line with the government’s target of universal access to clean cooking by 2028, by phasing out firewood and charcoal stoves before 2030. In rural areas in the SP scenario, this is mainly based on a transition to improved firewood stoves and to some extent bioethanol and biogas stoves. The KNeCS scenario sees a similar trend, yet with electric cooking with induction and pressure cookers increasingly used in rural areas and, in particular post-

2030, reducing the use of improved firewood stoves. In urban areas, the SP scenario sees a continuing use of LPG stoves and increasing use of bioethanol and improved woodstoves suitable for urban areas, for example pellet stoves, with minimal adoption of electric cooking. In contrast, the use of LPG stoves is decreasing steadily in the KNeCS scenario while there is a considerable increase in the use of electric cooking as well as ethanol stoves, reaching around 48% and 30%, respectively, in 2050.

From national strategy to county pathways

While a scenario analysis of aggregate countrywide pathways is a useful tool to support decision-making at the national level, it has limited value for providing insights to county governments, or facilitating a dialogue and coordination across government levels. Aggregate national pathways have limited relevance for stakeholders looking for county-specific pathways that consider local circumstances, and that might vary starkly from the national average.

As a national but county-resolved model, CORE-WESM allows for the consideration of national pathways, as shown in Figure 1, as well as the underlying pathways for each of Kenya's 47 counties. This analysis will focus on the variations across counties in terms of the distribution of relevant indicators, e.g., the use of different stoves, while also highlighting some counties. The focus counties are chosen to capture a selection of counties with diverging characteristics that could shape the clean cooking transition. Figure 2 provides an overview of the variation of key characteristics across counties, while Table 1 specifically lists key characteristics of the chosen counties.

Figure 2: Maps showing key characteristics across Kenya’s 47 counties, with focus counties highlighted with a red border. From the top left, the maps show the fraction of population living in urban areas²⁹, the fraction of households with access to electricity in 2019³⁰, the baseline fraction of households with clean cooking access as implemented in the model³¹, and the fraction of households without clean cooking access that could afford clean cooking solutions¹⁹.

Table 1: Key baseline characteristics of the focus counties. Population data are from KNBS²⁹, the remaining data sources are outlined in the caption of Figure 2.

Name	Population (millions)	Urban fraction	Clean cooking access	Fraction of households that can afford clean cooking solutions (of households without clean stoves)
Nairobi	4.4	100%	96%	57%
Bomet	0.88	3%	13%	32%
Turkana	0.92	15%	12%	21%

Figure 3: Fraction of key cookstoves used in counties by scenario, with focus counties highlighted with separate markers. The boxes include counties from the first quartile (Q1) to the third quartile (Q3), with the line showing the median (Q2). The whiskers capture all datapoints falling within $\pm 1.5 \times (Q1 - Q3)$ while outliers are shown as separate points.

Figure 3 shows the fraction of cookstoves used in each of the scenarios across all counties. It highlights a considerable variation in the use of stoves across counties in the base year and towards 2050 that is materially different to the national averages shown in Figure 1. This is particularly evident in the baseline use of LPG and woodstoves but also extends to, e.g., the increasing use of improved woodstoves, bioethanol, and electric cooking, particularly in the SP and KNeCS scenario.

The focus counties highlight the overarching differences and trends underpinning this distribution. As a completely urban county, Nairobi County sees only limited use of firewood and much higher use of LPG across all scenarios – although this is phased out in line with the national policy direction in the KNeCS scenario. Given its almost universal access to electricity and relatively higher levels of affordability across households, it sees a faster increase in the use of bioethanol stoves, as well as electric stoves in the

KNeCS scenario, than most other counties in the SP and KNeCS scenarios. Electric stoves and biofuel stoves meet 54% and 38% of cooking demand in Nairobi, respectively, in 2050. Given its low baseline use of traditional firewood stoves, the county does not see a substantial role of improved woodstoves in the transition to clean cooking. In contrast, in the predominantly rural counties of Turkana and Bomet, LPG use is much lower and only increasing noticeably in the BAU scenario, in which there is a shift to LPG use in rural areas alongside a continuing use in urban areas. Given low household electricity access, the use of electric cooking in the KNeCS scenario stays below 28% in Turkana, and the shift to cleaner cooking solutions in the SP and KNeCS scenarios is mainly based on a shift to improved woodstoves, and to some extent bioethanol stoves.

Figure 4: **Power sector implication of the three scenarios.** The rows are showing additional electricity demand and peak power demand for electric cooking for the three scenarios across all counties, as well as the aggregate national electricity consumption by sector for context.

Figure 4 shows the implications of the scenarios on the power sector in terms of the additional annual and peak electricity demand from electric cooking across counties. In the BAU and SP scenarios, the additional electricity demand is generally negligible across most counties, with Nairobi County as the only major outlier seeing around 0.4 TWh of electricity demand for cooking in 2020, increasing to 0.9 TWh and 1.1 TWh in the BAU and SP scenario, respectively, in 2050. The KNeCS scenarios sees a much larger increase in Nairobi, to around 7.3 TWh in 2050, as well as a number of other counties, while more than three quarter of counties, including Turkana and Bomet, still experience only an increase below 0.6 TWh, in line with a lower uptake in electric cooking and lower county population. In total, additional consumption of 34 TWh is expected in this scenarios, making up a fraction of 49% of the total electricity demand in 2050 projected for the scenario – although it is important to note a lower fraction would be expected if the scenario also models a push towards electrification across other sectors which is not considered here.

Similar trends can be observed for the peak electricity demand for cooking. In particular in the KNeCS scenario, peak demand across counties varies substantially, with Nairobi reaching 0.8 GW, while Turkana sees less than 0.1 GW – with a total additional peak demand of 3.9 GW across Kenya.

As intended given the focus of the analysis on representing KNeCS scenarios, the aggregate additional electricity generation requirements outlined above are broadly in line with the strategy. Yet, these are considerably higher than approximations based on daily electricity consumption for electric cooking as provided by, for example, Leach et al.³². This likely stems at least in part from challenges in the calibration of the modelled cooking energy demand projections for the KNeCS, which can lead to a potential overestimation of electricity consumption as electric cooking becomes more prevalent.

Nevertheless, the analysis highlights the diverging pathways and their implications across counties underpinning the KNeCS scenarios. In particular the implications on the power system also highlight the potential benefit for national power system planning that is contingent on spatial understanding of future electricity demand across counties to plan generation and transmission infrastructure.

Situating county planning in the national context

While the starting point for this analysis is a national strategy, which is assessed from a county perspective, key to the overall approach is the possibility to integrate county plans, enabling an examination of how they shape up or compare to a national strategy. Given only a very limited number of county energy plans have been launched and made publicly available, implementing county-driven scenarios is challenging. Instead, we compare the modelled adoption pathways with county-led scenarios from the county

energy plans of three counties, Kiambu, Kilifi, and Nyandarua. All three counties' energy plans include an analysis of three cooking pathways for the respective county, a business-as-usual (BAU), a stated policy (SP), and a sustainable development goals (SDG) scenario.

Figure 5 compares the fraction of stoves used in urban and rural areas in the three counties in the modelled KNeCS scenario, i.e., the adopted guiding pathway of the national government, with the targets for the SP and SDG scenario provided for the years 2028 and 2033 from each of the county plans.

Figure 5: Fraction of key cookstoves used in the KNeCS scenario in rural and urban areas of three counties with existing county energy plan. The markers in black show the stove adoption in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) and the grey markers for the Stated Policies (SP) scenario as outlined in the respective county energy plan. Note that the county energy plans, in contrast to the modelling results, take into account stove stacking, i.e., the use of more than one stove in a household for cooking purposes, and, thus, percentages can add up to more than 100%.

Comparing county analyses with the CORE-WESM modelling is challenging. For example, county energy plans take stove stacking into account while the modelling only considers households' main cooking solution. However, the comparison does highlight a certain alignment, as well as conflicting technological choices across county plans and the modelled national strategy. While the KNeCS envisions a decreasing role for LPG stoves, county plans, in particular for Kiambu and Nyandarua, assume high shares of households in rural and urban areas using LPG in both the SDG and SP scenarios. This could be partly due to the continuing role for LPG envisioned previously in national planning. For other stoves, varying degrees of alignment and mismatch can be observed across the three counties. For electric stoves, the selected CEPs generally assume a slower uptake than the KNeCS, with the exception of Kilifi's, which shows an increasing uptake of electric stoves that could support a transition roughly in line with the modelled KNeCS scenario. County scenarios also see a phase out of traditional woodstoves roughly in line with the KNeCS, where the limited use of traditional stoves in 2028 and beyond could be considered as part of households' secondary cooking solution.

Discussion

With the INEP process moving towards implementation, Kenya is approaching uncharted territory in its energy planning process. As this innovative multi-level planning framework takes further shape, establishing appropriate approaches and guidance for data flows and management, as well as modelling to underpin coordination and decision-making will be crucial. Efforts include for example the development of a minimum data guideline for data from county plans feeding into national energy planning, as well as a data platform to operationalise such data flows³³. Spatial modelling efforts, e.g., focusing on clean cooking³⁴ and electricity demand analysis³⁵, support a better geographic understanding of energy planning challenges.

This paper introduces a novel county-resolved whole energy system model for Kenya as a tool to support this process. The model is applied to a case study focused on the transition to clean cooking set out by the KNeCS, which highlights a number of key insights that can inform a common understanding and support a dialogue on clean cooking pathways across county and national governments.

While detailed national energy modelling has previously been performed to inform the KNeCS, this spatially resolved analysis highlights the substantial variations in the potential development of the cooking sector that can be expected across counties. This underlines that national aggregate pathways can hardly function as guiding pathways for county stakeholders looking to develop plans and targets aligned with national policy. For national stakeholders, county-explicit pathways highlight the potential role for place-

based national policies that target certain counties or areas with policy interventions based on county characteristics.

For example, meeting the government's key target of universal access to clean cooking by 2028 likely involves starkly different solutions across counties. In highly urban and electrified counties like Nairobi, this could be largely based on the continuing use of LPG, as well as increasing deployment of electric and bioethanol stoves. On the other hand, in mostly rural counties, meeting this target would likely involve a much larger role of improved woodstoves and to some extent bioethanol stoves. This could inform approaches to target limited resources, e.g., bioethanol, but also how to address diverging levels of clean cooking, including uneven distribution of potential benefits, e.g., on health.

The analysis also highlights the expected variation in the role of electric cooking across counties in a transition to a more electrified cooking sector. This is not only relevant for county planners looking to facilitate the uptake of electric stoves or alternatives clean cooking solutions where less relevant, but can also provide key spatial insights for national power system planning relying on spatially disaggregated demand projections to plan generation as well as transmission and distribution infrastructure.

Moreover, a comparison of a county-level representation of the KNeCS-aligned clean cooking pathway with three existing county energy plans highlights the misalignment between national strategy and county plans. For example, county plans suggest county governments' understanding of an increasing importance of LPG in the transition to universal access to clean cooking, while the KNeCS foresees a decreasing role. While this is partly to be expected given the lack of an established integrative processes as planned for the INEP, it underlines the challenges of siloed planning and the importance of establishing processes and tools that support the development of such plans in a coordinated fashion that leads to aligned and mutually reinforcing strategies and policy efforts at both scales involved.

While the analysis provides a number of relevant insights, it is also important to stress the limitations of the current approach and potential future work to address these shortcomings.

First, the analysis translates national scenarios into county-resolved pathways using a limited number of county characteristics. While this provides reasonably grounded pathways, this approach could be improved by examining and comparing different ways of such county disaggregation. These could also consider other important characteristics that shape stove adoption at the county level, such as LPG distribution infrastructure or accessibility to inform LPG uptake. If further such datasets characterizing counties become available and are integrated in the model, its optimization paradigm could potentially be more usefully applied to derived county-level

cooking solutions. Yet, with cooking technology choices being shaped by household circumstances and preferences, this is likely to remain challenging.

Second, while the analysis does include an initial comparison of county energy plans and the modelled county-national KNeCS-aligned pathway, it does not incorporate data and policy targets of such plans to develop county-led scenarios. With further CEPs being published and data sharing mechanism implemented, this would be an important exercise that could further strengthen the application of the model.

Third, with the focus of the analysis being on deriving county-resolved pathways for the cooking sector, the assessment of such pathways is limited to their impact on the power system. Future work could build on this effort and provide a more detailed assessment in terms of the costs and benefits of the transition across counties that could further enrich a dialogue across county and national governments.

Nevertheless, the case study highlights the potential use of the model as a tool to provide insights on energy system pathways that are coherent across scales and can also support a dialogue and common understanding among county and national stakeholders. This extends beyond just the cooking sector and can consider the entire energy system and interactions across sectors, in line with the cross-sectoral nature of the INEP itself.

This approach of multi-scale modelling also faces challenges, some of them compounded in LMIC contexts. This includes limited data availability, in particular spatially disaggregated datasets, that can support a detailed subnational representation of the energy system that makes such efforts salient to stakeholders. Institutional capacity to engage in such modelling processes can be constrained, in particular at subnational levels that can also see frequent staff turnover. This particularly applies to the development and operation of such a large multi-scale model, which is additionally exacerbated by increased computational requirements. Yet, if these can be addressed – with some initial solutions indicated in this analysis – this approach can play a helpful role in supporting multi-level governance of the energy system in Kenya and beyond.

Method

The analysis applies a county-resolved whole energy system model to conduct a quantitative assessment of three clean cooking scenarios.

CORE-WESM

The COunty-REsolved Whole Energy System Model (CORE-WESM) is an open-source whole energy system model developed to support integrated county-national energy planning in Kenya. It is a spatially disaggregated version of OSeMOSYS Kenya, a national whole energy system model of Kenya that has previously been developed and applied to

a number of different studies, including to support national policy development^{27,28,36}. CORE-WESM has been co-developed under UK PACT and CCG funded projects in discussions with a range of Kenyan stakeholders.

Similar to its national counterpart, the model is a technology-explicit, bottom-up optimization model based on the Open Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS) framework³⁷. It minimizes the cost of the deployment and operation of energy system technologies to meet exogenously defined energy service demands, while taking into account environmental, economic, or other constraints. It is generally used for scenario analyses considering medium- or long-term scenarios towards 2050 to support energy planning^{38,39}.

CORE-WESM incorporates all energy demand sectors – residential, transport, commercial, industry, and agriculture – as well as supply sectors, including a power system module and fossil fuel supply. In this regard, its strength lies in particular in examining system interactions across different sectors of the energy system.

In contrast to the national OSeMOSYS Kenya model, and many other national whole energy system models, CORE-WESM is underpinned by a detailed and flexible spatial structure based on the open-source fradoo framework¹⁴. fradoo is an add-on framework around OSeMOSYS that allows for a flexible definition and operation of energy system models across spatial scales. It facilitates, for example, defining system parts at different scales and aggregating certain regions for a specific model run. A flow diagram of CORE-WESM highlighting its structure and workflow is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: **Flow diagram of the CORE-WESM model highlighting data and processing steps.**

In the current version of CORE-WESM, the spatial representation of sectors is based on the importance to county planning, data availability, or focus of the analysis. Currently, the residential, commercial, and agricultural sectors as key sectors in CEPs are represented at county level, while others are modelled as national aggregate sectors. Nevertheless, the flexibility of the approach allows for other sectors that are relevant to county-level planning, including renewable energy resources and decentralised power generation, to be disaggregated in future.

CORE-WESM inherits its general temporal representation from the OSeMOSYS Kenya model, covering a 2019 -2050 horizon, with each year disaggregated into 48 timeslices. Yet, due to the computational complexity introduced through the spatial resolution of the model, temporal aggregation is applied to make the optimization computationally manageable. For the model runs in this analysis, 2019, 2020 and every fifth following year is represented. The intra-annual temporal resolution is aggregated to capture three representative periods. This includes day, night, and peak, which corresponds to the peak cooking demand, in order to still capture the peak demand requirements.

The detailed characterization of the energy system at county level requires a comprehensive set of county-specific data. As data availability is limited and varying across counties, not least depending on their progress with and scope of their CEP, CORE-WESM follows a three-tier hierarchical approach to data sourcing. First, an initial model data set is derived by downscaling national data from the OSeMOSYS Kenya model. This includes all relevant input parameters, including demand projections and the characterization of technology options. Second, county-resolved national datasets, e.g., from national data providers, can be integrated where available. Third, county-specific data from county energy plans or county administrations can be incorporated where available. This can in particular also link to and build on county-level modelling, for example existing efforts establishing tools and building capacity for county energy demand projections⁴⁰. This hierarchical approach enables the creation of a first-order but complete representation of the whole energy system across county and national level, which can be improved as and when additional data become available as part of the INEP process. A visual representation of hierarchical approach is provided in Figure 7.

Figure 7: **Hierarchical data approach of CORE-WESM.**

The downscaling converts the national aggregate model to a county-resolved model. Taking into account the sectors to be represented at the county level, it applies a mapping of technologies, fuels, and emission types to sectors in order to define which system elements to disaggregate. All input parameters entries associated with county sectors are then downscaled by creating a separate entry for each county and applying a sector-dependent proxy to scale values. For the residential sector, this uses population projections and urbanization for each county to scale parameters. For the commercial

and agricultural sectors, it applies the respective sectoral gross county product. Gross county products are derived by the Kenya National Bureau of Statistics and represent each county's contribution to Kenya's gross domestic product for a range of different sectors. For the purpose of this analysis, county-resolved datasets related to the cooking sector are integrated to improve the representation of the baseline and scenario pathways of this sector.

CORE-WESM includes a detailed representation of the cooking sector. Along with the remaining residential sector, cooking is represented separately for rural and urban areas in each county. For each area, it includes a broad set of different cookstove technologies, as shown in Figure 1, that can be deployed to meet the defined energy service demands. Their techno-economic characterisation is based on the national OSeMOSYS Kenya model for which the cooking sector was revised as part of a collaborative process during the development of the KNeCS. The baseline use of cookstoves across counties is based on data from the 2023/24 housing survey of the Kenya National Bureau of Statistics (KNBS)³¹ on the use of stoves and fuel in each county. Due to a lack of longitudinal data, this is assumed constant in the base years from 2019 to 2024. Given the aggregate way households are represented in the model, it only represents the main cookstove and cooking fuel for households, and does not consider fuel or stove stacking as such.

A more technical documentation of CORE-WESM and the model itself, including all data, are available online at github.com/ClimateCompatibleGrowth/CORE-WESM/.

Scenarios

The analysis examines three clean cooking scenarios previously developed to support the development of the KNeCS. The Business-As-Usual (BAU) scenario assumes continuing trends and technology adoption rates without any noticeable additional clean cooking interventions. The Stated Policies (SP) scenario assumes existing or stated policies towards clean cooking are implemented. This in particular includes the government's target of reaching universal access to clean cooking by 2028, but also other policy objectives including the reduction of biomass consumption by 50% by 2040 and increasing use of LPG for cooking. The e-cooking transition (KNeCS) scenario is the pathway adopted to underpin the KNeCS and has been developed as a balanced pathway through stakeholder discussions as part of the development of the strategy. A detailed description and assumptions underpinning these national scenarios are provided in the modelling report accompanying the KNeCS²⁸.

These national scenarios are implemented in CORE-WESM by introducing constraints on stove adoption in line with the national aggregate pathways modelled with the OSeMOSYS Kenya and shown in the KNeCS and its modelling report. For this, the national cookstove adoption pathways are disaggregated into county-level constraints following a three-step process outlined below.

First, the use of different types of cookstoves in the base years is defined across counties using the county-resolved datasets mentioned above.

Second, the county-level cookstove shares are iteratively derived for two milestone years, 2030 and 2050 through a three steps process. First, as a starting point, in each county, the stoves shares in the milestone year are assumed to be the same as in the previous period, i.e., the base years or previous milestone year. The difference between the aggregate of these initial assumptions and the national targets defined in the KNeCS scenarios is then calculated. This provides the extent to which the use of each stove needs to be increased or decreased to be in line with the national scenario pathway. Second, for the stoves with decreasing use, this reduction is allocated proportionally across counties based on their usage levels. Finally, for stoves with increasing use, this expansion is allocated across counties so as to offset the reduction in traditional stoves. The allocation of specific types of stoves is based on county characteristics that could shape adoption rates, such as previous use of traditional stoves, household electrification, and market segmentation. Table 2 describes the factors taken into account for each relevant stove.

Table 2: Overview over the factors considered for the disaggregation of national stove adoption to county level, including their source and application to stoves.

Factor	Description and Source	Applied to stoves
Previous use of traditional woodstoves	Previous fraction of cooking energy supplied by traditional woodstoves in the county in the base year or earlier milestone year.	Improved woodstove
Previous use of traditional charcoal	Previous fraction of cooking energy supplied by traditional woodstoves in the county in the base year or earlier milestone year.	Improved charcoal stove
Household access to electricity	Fraction of households with electricity access in the year in each county ³⁰ .	All electric stoves
Market segmentation	Fraction of households with either existing use of modern cooking solutions or that could afford such solutions based on the market segmentation performed for the KNCTS ¹⁹ . For improved charcoal and biomass stoves, the fraction of households without clean cooking access that are less likely to be able to afford clean cooking solutions is used.	All electric stoves, biofuel stoves, biogas stoves, LPG stove, improved charcoal and woodstoves

With base year and milestone years calculated, the third and final steps of the overall workflow uses linear interpolation to derive cookstoves shares between them.

Author contributions

Conceptualization: LH, SP; **Methodology:** LH, SP, A. Millot; **Software:** LH, A. Millot; **Data curation:** LH, MK, A. Mbutura, A. Millot, PL, MA, GM, MK, SP; **Writing- Original draft preparation:** LH, **Writing- Reviewing and Editing:** LH, MK, A. Mbutura, A. Millot, PL, MA, GM, MK, SP; **Funding acquisition:** SP.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by funding from the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) programme. CCG is funded by UK aid from the UK government. However, the views expressed herein do not necessarily reflect the UK government's official policies.

Data and code availability

The CORE-WESM model, including code, data, and documentation, is available in its GitHub repository at github.com/ClimateCompatibleGrowth/CORE-WESM/.

References

1. Fuso Nerini, F. *et al.* Mapping synergies and trade-offs between energy and the Sustainable Development Goals. *Nature Energy* **3**, 10–15 (2018).
2. Goldthau, A. & Sovacool, B. K. The uniqueness of the energy security, justice, and governance problem. *Energy Policy* **41**, 232–240 (2012).
3. Amundsen, H., Hovelsrud, G. K., Aall, C., Karlsson, M. & Westskog, H. Local governments as drivers for societal transformation: towards the 1.5°C ambition. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability* **31**, 23–29 (2018).
4. Hofbauer, L., McDowall, W. & Pye, S. Challenges and opportunities for energy system modelling to foster multi-level governance of energy transitions. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* **161**, 112330 (2022).
5. Government of Kenya. Constitution of Kenya 2010. (2010).
6. Government of Kenya. Energy Act. (2022).

7. Ngaira, C., Mbutura, A. & Barasa, M. *Exploring Frameworks for the Aggregation of Sub-National Energy Plans in Kenya (EFSEP-K)*.
<https://climatecompatiblegrowth.com/wp-content/uploads/Exploring-frameworks-for-the-aggregation-of-Subnational-energy-plans-in-Kenya-EFSEP-%E2%80%93-K.pdf> (2023).
8. Ministry of Energy and Petroleum. Energy Circular No. 1/2025. (2025).
9. Süsser, D. *et al.* Model-based policymaking or policy-based modelling? How energy models and energy policy interact. *Energy Research & Social Science* **75**, 101984 (2021).
10. Ministry of Energy and Petroleum. *Least Cost Power Development Plan 2024-2043*. <https://pppkenya.go.ke/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/Annex-4-LCPDP.pdf> (2024).
11. Ministry of Energy and Petroleum. *Kenya National Electric Cooking Strategy*. (2024).
12. Mwendwa, D. M., Leonard, A. & Hirmer, S. *Review and Comparison of Nakuru, Kitui and Narok County Energy Plans*. (2023).
13. Daly, M. *et al.* Addressing context-specific energy modelling risks and dynamics in low- and middle-income countries. *Nature Energy* 1–8 (2026) doi:10.1038/s41560-025-01962-y.
14. Hofbauer, L. Energy system modelling for multi-level governance of sustainable energy transitions. (UCL (University College London), 2025).
15. Gönenç, Y. & van Daalen, E. An Objective-Based Perspective on Assessment of Model-Supported Policy Processes. *Journal of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation* **12**, 27 (2009).

16. Star, S. L. & Griesemer, J. R. Institutional Ecology, 'Translations' and Boundary Objects: Amateurs and Professionals in Berkeley's Museum of Vertebrate Zoology, 1907-39. *Social Studies of Science* **19**, 387–420 (1989).
17. Taylor, P. G., Upham, P., McDowall, W. & Christopherson, D. Energy model, boundary object and societal lens: 35 years of the MARKAL model in the UK. *Energy Research & Social Science* **4**, 32–41 (2014).
18. Fields, N., Kinyanjui, B., Brown, E. & Howells, M. Energy Modelling Research Landscape in Kenya: A Systematic Review. (2025) doi:10.33774/coe-2025-7lmg3-v2.
19. Ministry of Energy and Petroleum. *Kenya National Cooking Transition Strategy*. (2024).
20. Ministry of Energy. *Bioenergy Strategy 2020*.
<https://www.energy.go.ke/sites/default/files/KAWI/Other%20Downloads/Bioenergy-strategy-final-16112020sm.pdf> (2020).
21. Kiambu County Government. *Kiambu County Energy Plan 2024-2028*.
22. Kilifii County Government. *Kilifi County Energy Plan 2025-2034*.
23. Nyandarua County Government. *Nyandarua County Energy Plan 2024-2028*.
24. Odhiambo-Abuya, I. & Owuor, M. Dissonance by design: How policy harmonization stifles affordable energy programs in Kenya. *The African Journal of Research on Policy Harmonization* **1**, (2025).
25. Ngeywo, E. & Wykes, S. *Vertical Collaboration for County Energy Planning in Kenya*.
26. Leone, E., Wykes, S., Cyoy, E. & Ogao, Y. *Accelerating Local Development through Inclusive Energy Planning: Lessons from Meru County, Kenya*.
<https://www.iied.org/22702iied> (2026).

27. Lubello, P., Oduor, J. & Pye, S. OSeMOSYS Kenya Whole Energy System Model. (2025) doi:10.5281/zenodo.15056038.
28. Ministry of Energy and Petroleum. *Kenya National Electric Cooking Strategy: Modelling Report*. (2024).
29. Kenya National Bureau of Statistics. 2019 Kenya Population and Housing Census. (2019).
30. Fields, N. *et al.* Demand starter data kit: Selected socio-economic and technical energy system demand modelling data for all 47 counties in Kenya. *Data in Brief* **60**, 111556 (2025).
31. Kenya National Bureau of Statistics. 2023/24 Kenya Housing Survey. (2024).
32. Leach, M. *et al.* Modelling the Costs and Benefits of Modern Energy Cooking Services—Methods and Case Studies. *Energies* **14**, 3371 (2021).
33. Kisaka, M. *et al.* *Integrating County Energy Plans into Kenya's Integrated National Energy Planning (INEP) Process (Forthcoming)*.
34. Khavari, B. *et al.* Integrated geospatial modelling for the achievement of universal energy access in Kenya. *npj Clean Energy* **1**, 12 (2025).
35. Millot, A., Kerekeš, A., Korkovelos, A., Stringer, M. & Hawkes, A. Electricity demand mapping from open-source data for low- and middle-income countries. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Transition* **9**, 100138 (2026).
36. Lubello, P. *et al.* Green hydrogen futures in LMICs: Opportunities for fertilizer and steel production in Kenya. *iScience* **28**, (2025).
37. Howells, M. *et al.* OSeMOSYS: The Open Source Energy Modeling System. *Energy Policy* **39**, 5850–5870 (2011).

38. Millot, A. *et al.* The map behind the roadmap—Introducing a geospatial energy model for utility-scale solar and wind power buildout in Kenya. *Cell Reports Sustainability* **1**, (2024).
39. Kihara, M. *et al.* Mid- to long-term capacity planning for a reliable power system in Kenya. *Energy Strategy Reviews* **52**, 101312 (2024).
40. Fields, N. *et al.* CORE-D: county resolution energy demand projections for multi-scale modelling and multi-level governance dialogues in Kenya. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Transition* **8**, 100131 (2025).